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Monitoring of Urban Nature-Based Solutions in Central European Context: Insights from Prague City Lab

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Abstract. European cities are increasingly adopting nature-based solutions (NbS) as essential strategies to adapt to climate change. As part of the Horizon Europe project NBSINFRA, Prague hosts one of five City Labs across Europe, focusing on implementing and monitoring NbS in diverse urban contexts. Key sites include the University Centre for Energy Efficient Buildings of the Czech Technical University (CTU) in Buštěhrad, where green roofs with various layering and substrates, rooftop constructed wetlands, and bioretention cells are studied; the CTU University Campus in where green roofs are implemented along with other urban greenery; and Českobrodská High School, featuring a green roof, green façade, and blue infrastructure for rainwater and greywater management. The monitoring of soil and near surface temperatures is done using autonomous compact sensors. Specific data on components of water balance are also collected. All data are organized in a centralized database to ensure consistency, accessibility, and reproducibility, supporting the evaluation of resilience indicators and the effectiveness of NbS in the City Lab Prague. Initial detailed mapping of plant species at these sites provided critical data on biodiversity. Historical data and forecasts have identified extreme heat and heatwaves as primary hazards. Finally, this paper highlights how the NbS monitoring across these sites enhances building and neighbourhood resilience to climate extremes, providing actionable insights for advancing urban planning strategies.

1. Introduction

Nature-based solutions are defined as strategies that use ecosystem services to address social and environmental challenges, such as climate change, water management and biodiversity loss, while ensuring sustainability and social inclusivity [1]. An NbS is characterized by its reliance on the benefits provided by nature, evaluated through the extent to which ecosystem services contribute to solving a clearly defined problem. These solutions emphasize the integration of ecological, social, and technological aspects to achieve sustainable development goals [2]. NbS include established approaches such as ecosystem-based adaptation focused on ecosystem restoration, ecosystem-based disaster risk reduction and green and blue infrastructure. NbS work by protecting, restoring, or sustainably managing ecosystems, whether natural, semi-natural, or created, to provide direct benefits to people [3]. The core strength of nature-based solutions lies

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in their ability to harness benefits from healthy, biodiverse, and resilient natural systems, offering a holistic approach to addressing environmental and social challenges [4].

Measures like green and blue infrastructure, such as wetlands and natural floodplains, reduce energy demands, help manage water and prevent flooding. NbS also foster biodiversity by creating habitats for various species, ensuring ecological balance while delivering economic and social benefits such as increased property values, tourism and recreational opportunities [5].

According to Krauze and Wagner [6], green infrastructure, such as green roofs and urban vegetation, plays a significant role in reducing urban heat island effects by improving evapotranspiration and shading. These measures help lower temperatures, enhance thermal comfort, and contribute to more comfortable cities during heatwaves or other extreme weather conditions. NbS offer significant advantages over conventional urban infrastructure.

As claimed by Ferrario et al. [7], green roofs lower air temperatures by up to 2°C and surface temperatures by 20°C, while parks and trees cool by 1.5–3°C and 0.5–2°C, respectively. In contrast, impervious urban surfaces worsen the urban heat island effect, raising temperatures by 3–7°C. NbS also cut stormwater runoff by 50–90%, while traditional infrastructure increases it 2–4 times, heightening flood risks. Their impact is 20–30% stronger in smaller towns than in dense cities. Standardized assessments and replicable strategies are key to maximizing NbS benefits in urban planning.

1.1 NBSINFRA project

This paper focuses on the results from the monitoring activities performed within the Horizon Europe project titled City Nature-Based Solutions Integration to Local Urban Infrastructure Protection for a Climate-Resilient Society (NBSINFRA) [8], which commenced in September 2023 and spans four years.

The project's core aim is to strengthen urban infrastructure resilience against both natural and man-made hazards by co-designing and co-creating NbS. By developing a robust methodology and toolkit, NBSINFRA seeks to provide a best-practice guide for fostering sustainable and resilient urban systems. The project will test existing and novel approaches in five designated City Labs located in Aveiro (PT), Fingal (IE), Prague (CZ), Cologne (DE), and Ruse (BG).

A key focus of the project is comparing infrastructure vulnerabilities with and without NbS through simulations and condition analyses. A literature review on how mitigating man-made hazards with NbS was already presented in a study by Felicioni et al. [9]

1.2 Scope and Objectives

This paper focuses on the implementation and monitoring of NbS in Prague as part of the Horizon Europe project NBSINFRA. It evaluates the effectiveness of green roofs, constructed wetlands, and bioretention cells at three key sites. The objectives include assessing thermal regulation, stormwater management, and biodiversity enhancement, collecting and analyzing relevant data, developing resilience indicators, and providing actionable insights for urban planners to enhance urban resilience to climate change.

2. Materials and Methods

The City Lab of Prague encompasses three distinct locations where NbS are tested and evaluated under real-world conditions. These sites function as experimental and collaborative environments, each representing unique urban settings that pose specific challenges and opportunities for NBS implementation. Historical data and climate projections indicate that

extreme heat and heat waves will be the primary hazard affecting these sites. The selected locations are as follows:

- A. University Centre for Energy Efficient Buildings (UCEEB), Czech Technical University (CTU): Situated in a peri-urban brownfield area on the outskirts of Prague, this site provides a platform for testing NbS in the context of energy-efficient building strategies.
- B. CTU University Campus (Prague 6): Located in the inner city, this area offers a complex urban environment for evaluating NbS in a densely populated setting.
- C. Českobrodská High School (Prague 9): An inner-city site that explores the integration of NbS within educational and community-focused spaces.

2.1 Plant species monitoring

A comprehensive plant species monitoring effort was conducted across these three locations between May and September 2024. This period was chosen to encompass various phenological phases, including flowering, seed set, and leaf senescence, enabling the documentation of both early and late-season species. The monitoring utilized survey plots to systematically document plant species in urban environments. Plots were selected to represent different habitat types, including lawns, ornamental beds, naturalized areas, green roofs, and disturbed urban zones. Key steps included species identification, abundance measurement, and ecological role classification. Collected data were recorded with GPS coordinates, species lists, and abundance metrics, then digitized for analysis, in particular in Geographic Information System (GIS) maps.

The findings highlight the potential of urban green infrastructure to enhance biodiversity and ecological services. The analysis not only documented plant species diversity but also evaluated their ecological roles in supporting urban sustainability, contributing to climate adaptation, and promoting biodiversity conservation.

2.2 Monitoring of NbS

The monitoring and evaluation of the specific NbS are listed in Table 1. This monitoring underscores how green roofs, bioretention cells, and hybrid systems enhance urban climate resilience, thermal regulation, and stormwater management.

The monitoring focuses on evaluating the thermal regulation and stormwater management capabilities of green roofs and bioretention cells.

To collect data, sensors were installed at various sites to monitor temperature fluctuations and soil moisture levels, supporting ongoing research into the effectiveness of green infrastructure in urban settings.

Table 1. Overview of NbS within the City Lab of Prague.

Site	NbS to monitor	Monitoring system
CTU UCEEB research centre	extensive green roof (GR) ultra-thin lightweight green roof (ULGR) hybrid constructed wetland-extensive GR (HGR) bioretention cells (BC) three weather stations (WS)	water content in the substrate – GR, ULGR, BC, HGR substrate and surface temperature - GR, ULGR, BC, HGR drone imaging Pressure head in the substrate - BC Outflow – BC, ULGR, CW-GR, GR Temperature through roof structure - ULGR

		Soil heat flux - ULGR Microclimate conditions - WS
CTU University Campus	extensive green roof	Substrate and surface temperature and substrate humidity Soil sampling – retention curve, grain size distribution
Českobrodská High School	biosolar green roof blue infrastructure – rain and grey water use	Substrate and surface temperature and substrate humidity Soil sampling – retention curve, grain size distribution

2.3 Evaluation of performance

After the data are collected for each NbS, the evaluation and assessment of thermal performance is considered, as well as water retention. However, a major challenge involves managing and interpreting the large volumes of data generated by monitoring systems. Ongoing analysis of collected data can provide insights into optimal irrigation practices and other management strategies. Yet, extracting actionable insights from this data often requires advanced analytical tools and expertise that may not be readily available to all stakeholders.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Ecosystem mapping and analysis

The plant species mapping in City Lab Prague was conducted across three sites, each representing distinct ecological and urban characteristics – Table 2 presents detailed data.

At the CTU University Campus, a mix of manicured green spaces, pedestrian areas, and semi-naturalized habitats was observed. The vegetation includes managed lawns, ornamental plantings, and spontaneous growth in less-maintained areas. This site provides an opportunity to study biodiversity within an academic and research campus influenced by frequent human activity. The survey revealed a complex blend of native, non-native, and invasive species. Native species play critical roles in supporting local biodiversity. However, invasive species threaten ecological balance. Management strategies should prioritize preserving native flora, mitigating invasive species spread, and enhancing ecological functionality.

The UCEEB research centre features both ground-level vegetation and green roofs, which serve as habitats designed to improve energy efficiency, stormwater management, and urban biodiversity. Ground-level vegetation includes landscaped areas and unmanaged spaces, reflecting interactions between native and non-native species.

Table 2. Site mapping.

Site	Total area	Constructed areas	Paved surfaces	Permeable surfaces
CTU UCEEB research centre	5.5 ha	3.1 ha	1.1 ha (58%)	3.2 ha (42%)
CTU University Campus	76 ha	31 ha	26 ha (75%)	19 (25%)
Českobrodská High School	1.3 ha	0.5 ha	0.5 ha (23%)	0.3 ha (77%)

Native plants such as *Festuca rubra*, *Achillea millefolium*, and *Prunus avium* contribute to biodiversity and ecological services. However, invasive species like *Solidago canadensis*, *Erigeron annuus*, and *Robinia pseudoacacia* pose significant threats. Effective maintenance should focus on controlling invasive species and promoting structural diversity to enhance microclimates, support resilience to climate change, and optimize soil health.

At the Českobrodská High School, a mix of maintained green spaces, ornamental plantings, and naturalized areas was documented. Although dominated by human-influenced vegetation, including ruderal and pioneer species, this location provides insights into the ecological contributions of green spaces in educational settings.

Across all sites, the vegetation reflects the heavy influence of human activity, with most woody plants resulting from intentional plantings. While no legally protected rare species or Red List species were identified, invasive species like *Robinia pseudoacacia* and *Ailanthus altissima* were detected, highlighting the need for active maintenance to prevent their spread.

3.2 Monitoring of green roofs

Since the 2018 vegetation season, experimental green roof test beds (two different growing media, planted with *Sedum* spp. cuttings and *Sedum* spp. carpets) and have been monitored at the UCEEB research centre to assess their capacity for thermal regulation and stormwater management [10]. Later, the study on ultra-thin green roof with sedum carpet plants was also initiated.

3.2.1 Thermal Regulation

Test beds with dense vegetation, planted with sedum carpets, showed superior thermal performance. Dense vegetation provided shading and minimized direct solar exposure to the substrate, resulting in lower peak temperatures. For instance, a maximum temperature of 45 °C was recorded. Conversely, sparsely vegetated beds, especially those with coarser substrates, exhibited higher peak temperatures of up to 55 °C due to the greater heat absorption of exposed dark surfaces. Long-term monitoring of surface temperatures was conducted on an ultra-thin green roof and a conventional roof. Figure 1 features an example of surface temperatures over a 14-day summer interval. Results show clearly the differences in peak temperature between the two types of roofing. While the surface temperature of the conventional roof reached up to 61 °C during the afternoon, the green roof surface peaked at around 31 °C. The thermal profile of the green roof exhibited a close correlation with the ambient air temperature, displaying minimal fluctuations.

3.2.2 Water Management

The water regimes of the test beds displayed significant variation based on substrate type and vegetation density. Beds with finer substrates and dense vegetation retained 71.8% of the total rainfall, demonstrating superior water retention and delayed runoff. In contrast, the roof with a coarser substrate and sparse vegetation retained only 66.2% of rainfall and exhibited the highest cumulative runoff. The moisture retained in densely vegetated beds further enhanced thermal performance through evaporative cooling, which helped moderate temperature extremes.

3.2.3 Implications for Green Roof Design

The findings emphasize the critical role of substrate selection and vegetation density in optimizing green roof performance. Test beds with finer substrates and dense vegetation proved most effective at both moderating temperature fluctuations and managing stormwater, making them ideal for mitigating urban heat island effects and reducing stormwater runoff. By integrating these features, green roofs can simultaneously enhance urban climate resilience and contribute to sustainable water management strategies.

The monitoring of these test beds continues, providing ongoing insights into the long-term performance and potential of green roofs in urban environments.

Figure 1. Comparison of surface temperatures on a conventional roof (grey), a green roof (green), and air temperature (red) in two meters during the summer period.

3.3 Monitoring of infiltration swales

This specific monitoring activity focuses on the hydrologic behaviour of bioretention cells at the UCEEB research centre. Two identical cells were built, one collecting rainfall from a 38 m² roof (BC1) and the other undergoing controlled ponding experiments with extreme rainfall (BC2). Both featured a biofilter of sand, compost, and topsoil. A monitoring system with sensors tracked water balance and biofilter water potential. The methodology for rainfall-runoff analysis was developed for datasets collected during the first vegetation season of 2018, and monitoring has continued since [11].

3.3.1. Water management

The water regime of BC1, supplied with natural rainfall, demonstrated high efficiency in moderating stormwater discharge. The overall runoff coefficient was 0.72, with 87% of the total water supplied being discharged and 13% retained through evapotranspiration. Analysis of 17 rainfall-runoff events revealed runoff coefficients ranging from 0.17 to 1.18, primarily influenced by antecedent moisture conditions and rainfall intensity. Peak outflow reduction varied between 75% and 97%, highlighting BC1's strong ability to reduce peak stormwater flows. The water regime of BC2, used for ponding experiments with extreme rainfalls, exhibited a high runoff coefficient of 0.86, indicating lower retention capacity. Peak outflow reduction ranged from 19% to 30%, significantly less than in BC1.

These results highlight the effectiveness of bioretention cells in reducing peak stormwater flows. However, performance is notably affected by factors such as initial soil moisture content, rainfall depth and shape, and soil structure.

3.4 Monitoring of hybrid green roof systems

At the UCEEB research centre, hybrid green roofs are studied for their integrated approach to surface temperature regulation and water management. These systems combine a shallow (25 cm) constructed wetland with a green roof, serving a dual purpose: treating greywater and providing the environmental benefits of green roofs. As described by Petreje et al. [12], greywater is first pre-treated in the constructed wetland and then used to irrigate the green roof. The roof system consists of several layers, including a geotextile base, 3-5 cm mineral wool for water retention and capillary distribution, and 3-7 cm growing medium incorporating recycled

materials such as recycled building demolition waste with a major proportion of recycled crushed bricks and, in one test setup, and biochar derived from sewage sludge in another one. The top layer features a sedum mat to provide vegetative cover. The hybrid green roof system is monitored on two elevated experimental plots of approximately 2 m² each and on the roof of the research centre of approximately 70 m².

3.4.1 Thermal Performance

The hybrid system demonstrated significant thermal regulation benefits. Surface temperature peaks were dampened and delayed with increasing depth, with the bottom layer's peak temperature occurring nearly nine hours after the ambient air temperature peak. The use of sewage sludge-based biochar in the growing medium enhanced plant growth due to large amounts of nutrients, increasing evapotranspiration and further reducing surface temperatures.

3.4.2 Water Management

The hybrid roofs also excelled in stormwater management. Pre-treated greywater flowed through the mineral wool and growing media, with the biochar-amended substrate exhibiting superior water retention. This led to reduced runoff and increased evapotranspiration rates. Runoff coefficients ranged between 0.47 and 0.56, with the biochar system achieving lower coefficients due to its higher retention capacity and enhanced vegetation growth.

3.5 Monitoring of thermal performance

As part of City Lab Prague's exploration of green infrastructure, TOMST TMS-4 sensors were deployed at two locations, respectively at the Českobrodská High School and at the National Library of Technology in Prague, located within the CTU University Campus. These sensors measure soil moisture, surface temperatures, and substrate temperatures in experimental green roofs with substrate depths of 7–10 cm. The collected preliminary data from the fall 2024 and winter 2024-2025 period provides detailed insights into temperature fluctuations across different layers of the green roofs. Interestingly, it was shown that green roofs effectively prevented the temperature of the substrate from dropping below freezing temperature during the majority of the time due to the release of heat from phase transition. This was observed despite the air temperature above the roof frequently reaching sub-zero temperature and demonstrating the ability of a green roof to significantly equalize the temperature of the building's envelope.

4. Conclusions

The research presented in this paper is part of the ongoing work within the NBSINFRA European project, with a particular focus on the preliminary data obtained from the monitoring activities of three sites where NbS are implemented.

Findings from the ecosystem mapping highlight the importance of managing invasive species while preserving native plant diversity to enhance the ecological value of urban green spaces. For example, ground-level vegetation at the UCEEB centre demonstrates adaptability to climate change due to the presence of drought-tolerant and deep-rooted species. By promoting native plants that improve soil health and provide essential ecosystem services such as shading and moisture retention, these spaces can enhance long-term resilience to rising temperatures and increased evaporation.

The monitoring activities primarily assess the thermal performance and water management of NbS. For instance, green roofs at the UCEEB centre recorded a maximum temperature reduction of up to 10°C, with dense vegetation retaining 71.8% of rainfall, compared to 66.2% for sparser vegetation. These findings are organized in a centralized database to ensure consistency,

accessibility, and reproducibility, and underscore the potential of NbS to mitigate extreme heat, manage stormwater, and support biodiversity, offering valuable insights for urban planners seeking to integrate NbS into urban infrastructure for more sustainable and resilient cities.

Future management efforts across all Prague City Lab sites should prioritize controlling invasive species, enhancing structural diversity, and optimizing the ecological functionality of urban habitats to support biodiversity and contribute to sustainable urban ecosystems.

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